

very low at 60 DT. There was no relationship between plant height and herbage yield at 40 DT and a negative association at 60 DT (the sheath and culm became the dominant plant part as rice plants grew taller, especially in traditional tall cultivars).

High herbage yields can be obtained from rice varieties with vigorous growth during vegetative stage. Cultivar differences should be considered in herbage production. ■

Table 1. Herbage yield at 40 and 60 DT of 24 rice cultivars grown with irrigation. IRRI, 1989 wet season.

Rice cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)	
	40 DT	60 DT
<i>Deepwater rice</i>		
Ban Daeng	0.82	1.39
Huntra 60	0.88	2.00
Khao Hoi	0.74	1.59
Khao Kaset	0.84	1.53
Khao Lod Chong	1.05	1.95
Khao Mali	1.14	2.06
Khao Praguad	1.10	1.89
Khao Puang Nak	0.66	1.38
Khao Rachinee	0.93	1.88
Leb Mue Nahng 111	0.88	1.56
Luang Pratharn	1.11	1.76
Mali Tawng	0.93	1.59
Nahng Khiew	0.93	1.47
Pan Tawng	1.21	1.98
Pin Gaew 56	0.84	1.25
Plai Ngahm	0.83	1.38
RD19	0.91	1.65
Sai Bua	0.93	1.29
Sam Ruang	0.83	1.39
Tapow Gaew 161	0.88	1.83
<i>Lowland rice</i>		
B4259	1.16	1.98
Binato	1.20	-
H4	1.32	1.64
IR29723-143-3-2	0.90	1.78
LSD (0.0.5)	0.23	0.44

Table 2. Relationship between herbage yield and growth parameters of 24 rice cultivars at 40 and 60 DT.^a IRRI, 1989 wet season.

Parameter	40 DT	60 DT
Active leaves wt (t/ha)	+0.948**	+0.816**
Leaf area index	+0.714**	+0.730**
Shoot wt (t/ha)	+0.878**	+0.536**
Sheath and culm wt (t/ha)	+0.766**	+0.137ns
Dead leaves wt (t/ha)	+0.266ns	+0.247ns
Tillers (no./m ²)	+0.334ns	+0.422*
Tiller wt (g)	+0.129ns	-0.283ns
Root wt (g/m ²)	+0.016ns	+0.122ns
Height (cm)	+0.005ns	-0.450*

^a Significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ns = nonsignificant.

Ratooning ability and potential herbage production from ratoon crops of rice cultivars

T. Kupkanchanakul, B. S. Vergara, and K. Kupkanchanakul, Agronomy, Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI

A rice ratoon crop has high potential for both grain and herbage production. However, most studies on rice ratooning have emphasized grain yield.

Using the herbage from a ratoon crop to provide a continuous supply of ruminant feed after harvest of the main rice crop has received little attention.

We evaluated the ratooning ability and potential herbage production from the ratoon crops of 20 deepwater and 4 lowland rices in irrigated fields at IRRI in the 1990 dry season. Cultivars were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Main crop straw was cut 15 cm aboveground 7 d after harvest and 60 kg N/ha surface applied. The field was

irrigated to 1-5 cm water depth throughout the ratoon crop.

Of 24 cultivars studied, only 17 produced ratoons (see table). Deepwater cultivars Huntra 60, Khao Rachinee, and Luang Pratharn had very good ratooning ability, similar to that of lowland cultivars.

Plants were sampled 30 and 60 d after ratooning (DAR) and at maturity of the ratoon crop to measure biomass yield (excluding the 15-cm stubble). Deepwater rice cultivars with high ratooning ability showed high biomass yield at 30 and 60 DAR, indicating the potential of a ratoon rice crop as forage during the dry season where natural forage in rice areas is limited.

Cultivars with high ratooning ability also produced higher grain yield, suggesting the potential for grain yield from ratoon crop in areas where water is available.

Herbage and grain production from a ratoon rice crop might be another approach to increasing production, adding crop value, and increasing land use efficiency and farmer income, especially in single-crop deepwater rice areas. ■

Ratooning ability and production of ratoon crops. IRRI, 1990 dry season.

Rice cultivar	Ratoon hills (% of main crop)	Biomass yield ^a (tha)			Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
		30 DAR	60 DAR	Maturity	
<i>Lowland rice</i>					
B4259	59	1.18	4.89	7.53	2.3
Binato	56	1.41	5.44	8.45	2.9
H4	56	1.29	4.44	9.43	2.3
IR29723-143-3-2	65	1.48	4.42	8.74	2.6
<i>Deepwater rice</i>					
Ban Daeng	11	-	-	-	-
Huntra 60	72	3.30	6.75	10.28	2.3
Khao Hoi	0	-	-	-	-
Khao Kaset	23	0.80	3.50	6.14	1.6
Khao Lod Chong	20	0.85	3.40	5.35	1.1
Khao Mali	10	-	-	-	-
Khao Praguad	29	0.65	3.47	9.08	2.0
Khao Puang Nak	9	-	-	-	-
Khao Rachinee	64	3.30	8.85	9.40	2.7
Leb Mue Nahng III	0	-	-	-	-
Luang Pratharn	59	1.93	8.80	12.92	2.7
Mali Tawng	0	-	-	-	-
Nahng Khiew	13	-	-	-	-
Pan Tawng	43	1.11	4.28	9.25	2.5
Pin Gaew	0	-	-	-	-
Plai Ngahm	4	-	-	-	-
RD19	32	0.91	2.43	5.12	1.2
Saibua	0	-	-	-	-
Sam Ruang	0	-	-	-	-
Tapow Gaew 161	0	-	-	-	-
LSD (0.05)	18	1.51	2.70	ns	1.1

^a Cultivars with less than 20% ratoons were not sampled.